
Emerging Trends in Animated Advertisement and its impact on consumer buying behaviour

¹Dr.Lakshman K, ²Yatindra Kumar Jain, ³Yuvaraj Grandhi, ⁴Reet S Jain, ⁵Vysak V, ⁶Kierthan Reddy

¹Associate Professor & Head, Assistant Dean-Student Affairs, Jain University-CMS, Bengaluru, Karnataka
^{2,3,4,5,6}Students, Jain University-CMS, Bengaluru, Karnataka

Abstract:

Animated ads are visual statements which are dynamic in nature and are majorly used for advertising and promoting purposes. This study aimed to analyze the relationship between animated advertisements and its effect on consumer buying behavior. This study revealed how awareness contributes to an advertisement's favourable consumer perception. It also investigated how consumers' buying behavior is influenced before and after watching these animated advertisements. Individuals from various age groups participated in this study. The research was conducted using a qualitative research method and was based on a questionnaire to which a sample of 266 consumers who had viewed animated advertisements in various situations had responded. Participants were asked about their perceptions of animated advertisements, including their views on the level of engagement, the effectiveness of the advertisements in conveying messages, and the impact of these advertisements on their buying behavior. The results emphasized that the animated advertisements have a real time positive impact on consumer buying behavior, by increasing attention, eliciting positive emotions, enhancing brand recall and value. This study concluded that the effects of animated advertisements on consumer buying behavior are substantial, and research has shown that they can be a highly effective means of reaching and influencing consumers. Modern visual advertisements today view animated ads as a necessary tool since they influence consumer perception, capture their attention, and eventually result in sales.

Keywords:

Animated advertisements, Consumer behaviour, Buying behaviour, Advertisements, Emotions.

Introduction:

Advertising is a powerful tool which alone not only attracts buyers, but also gives them information about the product and brand name, and builds customer trust. Most businesses use different forms of advertising to promote their goods or services. Goods or services can be advertised on several media such as print, radio, television and digital media. Advertising is an important part of trade and commerce and it benefits the business in various ways. Building brand awareness and spreading the word among potential buyers, is the main benefit of advertising. Besides creating brand awareness, businesses can also advertise special promotions, discounts and other offers with a view to increase their business. Rapid business expansion has led to increased competition, which in turn has forced brands to set themselves apart. However, regular advertising helps manage competitive forces in the market. An advertisement with good content builds goodwill. It should be noted that other supporting factors like superior quality products and better services also enhance the brand reputation, making it worldwide recognizable. Advertising educates the masses by sharing information about the use of a product, its benefits and also the diverse uses of certain products, if any. This makes them more comfortable and convinced to buy the product. Advertisements have the ability to increase the audience base from current audience to potential customers. However, it must be noted that wrong marketing efforts could lead to waste of time and money.

Evolution of Advertisements:

The invention of video advertising has become a major turning point in the history of advertising. In ancient times, advertising was conducted by word of mouth. With the invention of the printing press, advertisements gradually started to appear in the newspapers in the 17th century, and boomed in 18th century. In the United States, the first newspaper advertising appeared in 1704. Nineteenth century was the growth phase of advertising as an industry, which led to the establishment of advertising agencies. At that period the agencies functioned as brokers for space in the newspapers (Sagar Joshi, 2022). Later on in the early 1800s, billboard advertising gained popularity. Many companies opted for indirect advertising, since direct advertising was considered to be an expensive option. Agencies started creating advertising messages, including the copy and the artwork. By the 1920s, agencies took up the complete task right from planning and executing, to placement in various media. Sears was the first company to launch their direct mail campaign in 1892. They received two thousand new orders by posting more

than eight thousand postcards. This move encouraged other businesses to increase their advertising expenditures. As time passed by, advertising developed in other media such as direct mail, radio and television. The 1900s to 2000 is referred to as 'The Golden Age' of advertising. Radio and television took a different approach towards advertising, which took advertising to a whole new level. In the early 20th century, they were being used by more than 30% of the world's population.

In the year 1922, radio advertising was launched. This turned out to be a big hit. Advertisements were broadcasted by the radio stations at different time slots, which introduced new and existing brands to the listening audience. The success of the radio ads paved the way for television advertising. The first TV commercial was aired in 1941. It was the Bulova Watch Company that aired the first TV commercial, which was a ten seconds advertisement, and was viewed by 4,000 viewers in New York city. Organizations soon began investing heavily in advertisements, which enabled them to express their brand's uniqueness and engage their target audience. Later on, in the 1950s, businesses began to introduce characters for the purpose of advertising. One such example is the cartoon character Tony the Tiger which was introduced by Kellogg's. Furthermore, businesses started to focus a lot on advertising to promote brand awareness, instead of concentrating only on sales.

However, those were not the only places one could see advertisements. Advertisers managed to seek attention and communicate their messages by placing advertisements on bus stops, buildings, train and metro stations etc. Mobile advertising was also introduced, where advertisements were placed on vehicles like taxis, vans, buses, trucks etc. These have also become popular inside trains, metros and other public and private vehicles. As time passed, advertising grew rapidly and became widespread since the early 2000s, ever since the internet has taken over. With the extensive use of the internet, focus was shifted from the traditional offline ones, more towards the digital ones. The first online advertisement was created in 1994. At first, brands faced various challenges. In the early 1970s, e-mail advertising was very popular. Brands advertised their products internationally through e-mails and were able to engage in a global audience. In 2006, Google bought YouTube and started offering video adverts to companies. YouTube is thought to have one of the highest viewership rates. After Instagram was acquired by Facebook in 2013, Instagram advertising were introduced.

Video is one of the most powerful marketing strategies in the digital age. It's a versatile strategy with strong conversion rates, engagement rates, and the capacity to communicate clearly in a variety of various circumstances. Videos are a fantastic technique to raise brand exposure and user engagement (Inzamamur, 2021). But when they're animated, the levels of engagement soar. Animation employs advertising in a more imaginative way, offering brands and enterprises the advantage of making a lasting impact on both present and potential customers. Customers now have a better grasp of the company, its values, and how they can assist them. An expertly designed animated ad boosts website traffic, Google search engine optimisation, and conversion rates.

A study statistics on video marketing in 2020 was published in an article by Smart Insights. According to the article, 92% of marketers believe that video marketing is growing more important. Hence they felt the need to incorporate it in their strategies. Additionally, it was said that 53% of consumers interact with a brand after viewing a social media video. Animation history has always included advertising. Use of attractive colors, jingles, pleasant music, humor and interesting characters are examples of potential unconditioned stimuli used in commercial ads that have a deep influence on the target audience (Moana Thompson, 2019). Animation is well known for its aesthetic charm. By capturing a sequence of still photos, drawings, objects, or people in different locations of incremental movement, it is possible to give the appearance of continuous motion in motion movies. It is a highly effective design tool used to capture viewer interest and attention. Animation is classified into various categories. The most common of them are clay animation, computer generated imagery and puppet animation. In computer generated imagery, computers perform the task of creating a variety of graphics, 2D or 3D animation, objects or rendering (David Dillas Kirsten, 2015). 3D animated figures are used in puppet animation, which move gradually in each frame of the movie. Pixilation is a type of animation that uses people and other live subjects that are progressively shot in different poses. These are now the most often used form of animation in movies and TV advertising.

Animated advertisements have become a popular marketing tool for businesses looking to reach and engage with their target audience. The use of animation and graphics in advertisements can be a highly effective way to convey complex messages, capture the attention of viewers, and ultimately influence consumer buying behavior. The main goal of advertisement is to promote sales. It is a form of communication widely used to try and persuade consumers to purchase a particular product or service. Advertisers try to seek customers' attention with visual stimulations, explicit messages, convincing slogans, brand ambassadors etc., in order to convince them that their brand is better than others. This study aims to examine the effects of animated advertisements on consumer buying behavior, with a focus on how these advertisements can impact the cognitive and emotional processing of potential customers.

Corporations and advertising agencies have embraced animation as a way to showcase products and services, while engaging consumers in emotional and rational ways. In the present day, animated advertising has been shaped by new technologies such as digital production and distribution. The capacity of animators to build scenes and universes that a live action camera crew cannot access or replicate is one of the key benefits of utilising animation in advertising. These manufactured surroundings are utilised to arouse desire and the sense of possibility, which can subsequently be brought to life by persuading the target market to buy the product. Animation is also a relatively inexpensive process (David DillasKirsten, 2015).

Animation not only provides a compelling alternative to live-action videos, but it also enables the depiction of ideas that would be impossible to generate otherwise. For instance, you can animate a computer's internal workings but not film them. It is a great way to convey technical and complex ideas or messages in the form of a short story. Additionally, it gives marketers the ability to convey complicated concepts in a clear, comprehensive, and straightforward way for maximum retention in the shortest amount of time. Animated marketing is full of endless possibilities. It can be fun, imaginative, creative and entertaining. Finding a fun and successful approach to deliver a tale to the audience that they will remember for a very long time is the fundamental goal of animation advertising. The target audience is more likely to pay attention to animation than standard commercials because animation is frequently employed for fun rather than as a marketing technique. A good animated advertisement helps to boost the brand identity of the corporation and isolate it from the other businesses working in the same industry. Nearly 85% of marketers have testified that video marketing boosts traffic to their websites (NadyaFedrunova, 2021).

Animated advertisements make a product unique in its own way. The combination of visual and textual content is the best way to improve content marketing and make it unique, entertaining and engaging. It is believed that an average viewer will skim-read only 28% of words published in an advertisement, which probably will not convince him to become a loyal customer. Many entrepreneurs think that animated video production is an expensive option. Animated videos come in handy here, as it is much easier and cost effective to edit the message or visuals, rather than to reshoot the whole video. It keeps the content fresh, while maintaining a lower budget. To sum it up, we can say that animation marketing is a powerful and affordable marketing tool that helps to boost brand awareness and makes marketing strategy more effective. Various businesses are plunging into animation marketing - be it explainer videos, simple motion graphics, emails or newsletters (Ninja Studio, 2021).

Historical Review of Animation

Theatrical cartoons started airing on television in 1930, and due to production costs, animated cartoons started to debut in the early 1940s. Animation was commonly broadcast on TV during this time as a non-commercial experiment. Producers at the time were attempting to exert a lot of creative control over the cartoon genre (Cohen 1992). The global animation market was worth US \$24 million at the end of 2004. (NASSCOM 2002 Report). According to Roncarelli (2001), the total cost of producing commercial computer animation worldwide was expected to be \$25.4 billion in 1999. The market is still expanding very quickly. Advertising, motion pictures, television, design engineering, video games, location-based entertainment, and the Internet have all experienced growth in these areas.

Animation, a visual form of entertainment, has developed into a character-based industry with the potential to grow by providing digital material to media like the Internet and mobile devices. The creation of animated TV series and movies, the sale of video titles, and the sale of items with animated characters are further potential advantages of the animation sector. Modern technology has given rise to increasingly sophisticated computer graphics that enable animation to be used in computer games, TV advertising, and big-budget movies.

Animation is the process of simulating movement by connecting a number of slightly varied graphics (Wilson 2005). Animation is understood to mean creation in a universe beyond our wildest dreams. In the present entertainment industry, animation has gained popularity as a new tool for commercial design and as a genre of visual art. When talking about animated figures made of plasticine, clay, or other pliable materials, the term "clay animation" is used (Frierson 1994; Furniss 1998). Additionally, clay animation is now frequently seen in both films and advertisements.

Need of the study

Very less research has been done on animated advertising. Thus, it still belongs to a very young genre of advertisement design. This study intends to investigate the impacts of animation and how it relates to cognitive behaviour in people. The design and substance of advertising are frequently identified as a key aspect in study in psychological studies on animated advertisements and emotional reaction. Advertising clutter is produced by a large number of advertisements in multiple formats on one web page. This diminishes consumer memory of online

ads and enhances advertisement avoidance. Advertisement viewing is impacted by how different advertisement formats are perceived by online consumers. Investigating how online advertising attributes like format and animation affect consumers' attention and memory, is crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of online advertising. So it is essential to research on how consumers view different online advertising formats and their respective efficacy is still in its early stages.

Objectives

1. To investigate the factors that make animated commercials attractive to consumers.
2. To evaluate the superiority of animated commercials in communicating messages in comparison to non-animated commercials.
3. To analyze the persuasiveness of animated commercials in affecting the purchase decision of consumers.

Literature Review:

Babu,(2018)examined the significant impact that cartoon characters played in product marketing, particularly through advertisements, as well as how these children made decisions while shopping. The findings indicated that animation had little to no impact on attention. Despite this, a significant interaction effect between animation and advertisement type showed that advertisement format influenced the impact of animation. When people were engaged in other things, animation had a good influence on attention to skyscrapers but a negative one on attention to banners (Kuisma, Simola, Uusitalo, Öörni, 2010). Another research conducted by Manaf&Alallan, (2017) investigated how animation affects the effectiveness of advertisements by analyzing consumers' (cognitive and affective) reactions to animated advertisements in terms of their desire to purchase, while also taking into account the importance of involvement. Given that involvement is the mechanism by which consumers' motivation moderates the relationship between attitude formation and exposure to advertisements, it has been assumed that consumers who are highly involved in the product can better recall the advertisement and form more favourable attitudes towards the brand, including purchase intentions. Shuja et.al, (2018)determined whether utilizing animated characters in kid-targeted advertising was effective. The research was quantitative and of the causal research kind. Primary school going kids from nine different schools in various parts of Karachi, Pakistan, made up the study's respondents. It was advised that businesses utilize these engaging and appealing animated cartoon characters to improve brand recognition and recall. Jin, (2006) classified many forms of animation and live action used in television advertisements, the study sought to investigate the effects of animation and its relationship to human cognitive and affective processes. Somra, (2020)purposed of this research was to determine whether or not students could infer the intended meaning and idea from the animated TV advertisements for Vodafone. The findings showed that students' interpretation of complex media messages, such as those in animated Vodafone advertisements, was significantly influenced by their media literacy.Huang et.al (2011)investigated the relationships between animated spokes-characters, the effects of advertisement communication, and buy intentions, this study focused on animated spokes-characters and the involvement idea. If the message of the advertisement was compelling and persuasive, viewers or listeners would be likely to adopt a favorable opinion of the advertised goods.

Callcot and Lee(2013)used content analysis to look at animated spokes-characters and animation in television commercials. In this study, the majority of spokes-characters were human, animal, or product personifications. Television advertising with some animation had better effects on information retention (Khanum, Shareef, Khanam, 2015). Wu et.al(2022) studied examined how the addition of 3D animated agents affected the effectiveness of video advertisements in a virtual reality setting. Auken and Lonial(1985) examined how kindergarten, second, fourth, and sixth grade kids perceive a stimulus set that includes both human and animated characters. The justification was based on the possibility for deception in animation as well as potential moral and legal issues that could arise from the usage of cartoon characters in advertising. Scaling assessed similarity data results showed that the questioned school-grade categories had comparable perceptual structures and that an animate/human perceptual cue was presumably influencing perceptions. The findings also supported the use of simple judged similarities and multidimensional scaling for assessing children's perceptions.

Jain et. al (2022) studied anthropomorphic characters were appropriate for use in environmental communication. It looked into the qualities that made them effective communicators who encouraged sustainable behavior. Findings implied that spokespeople could effectively communicate to encourage environmentally friendly practices like recycling. Future research directions were provided, along with theoretical and practical ramifications. Diao and Sundar(2004)animation affected online consumers and how they responded to and remembered Web advertisements. In a mixed-design factorial experiment, all participants were exposed to four online portal websites, each of which had an animated or static banner advertisement and an equally animated or static pop-up

advertisement. Khan and Khanum(2021)examined the audience's needs that animation in food TV advertising satisfies and to determine whether those needs alter at various levels of animation. Animated TVCs meet needs for greater emotion and stress release. Findings demonstrated that when TV commercial animation varies, so do the viewer needs that it satisfies. The more animation is used in advertisements, the more effective and satisfying it is for releasing stress. Similar to this, the audience's requirement for cognitive stimulation is met to a greater extent the less animation is used in an advertisement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the modern period, animated characters play a significant role on how cartoon characters from movies are incorporated into kid-friendly products like chocolate, food, toys and bags. In order to gather quantitative data, a survey was conducted among a sample of consumers who had been exposed to animated advertisements. The survey consisted of a series of closed-ended questions designed to gather information about the impact of animated advertisements on consumer purchasing behavior, as well as demographic information about the respondents. Participants were requested to fill the survey anonymously. 266 responses were received of convenience sampling..Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis were used to analyse the survey data in order to find meaningful connections between animated commercials and customer purchase patterns. This study provides a general summary of purchasing behavior toward animation/ animated characters. This study also provided a better understanding of the marketing tactics used by companies to enhance sales of specific items by using animated characters as part of their product representation. Primary data collection methods have been used to obtain the data for the study. A primary poll based on the suggested topic has been carried out to find out how popular cartoon commercials are among viewers. The survey was administered online to ensure a large and diverse sample size, and had been designed to be user-friendly and easily accessible to all participants.

Hypotheses

This study focused on three hypothesis to validate the effectiveness and impact of animated advertisements on consumer behaviour.

1. Animated commercials are appealing to consumers due to their ability to create a unique and engaging visual experience. The use of imaginative characters and storylines effectively captures the viewer's attention and enhances brand recall.

Ho: Features such as characters, music, product and illustrations of animated commercials are not attractive to consumers.

H1: Features such as characters, music, product and illustrations of animated commercials are attractive to consumers.

2. Animated commercials are found to be more effective in delivering messages compared to non-animated commercials because they use captivating visuals and imaginative storytelling to engage the viewer. This results in better brand recall and a stronger emotional connection to the advertised product or service.

Ho: Animated commercials are effective in delivering the intended message to consumers.

H1: Animated commercials are not effective in delivering the intended message to consumers.

3. Animated commercials are found to be more persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers compared to non-animated commercials, due to their ability to create an emotional connection with the viewer through the use of engaging visuals.

Ho: Animated commercials are persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers.

H1: Animated commercials are not persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers.

Data analysis and interpretation

The first qualitative study is conducted to validate the data using the Chronbach's Alpha techniques where the data is proved to satisfy the requirement of the test with the alpha value >0.7 .

Case Processing Summary

		N	%	Cronbach's Alpha
Cases	Valid	266	100.0	0.773
	Excluded ^a	0	0	
	Total	266	100.0	

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 1: Reliability test using Chronbach's Alpha

The study carried a hypothesis testing to understand the features of animated commercials are attractive to consumers. The significance of the features of animated ads on consumers' purchase decisions was tested using One-Way ANOVA.

ANOVA

CPD

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	15.947	5	3.189	7.426	.000
Within Groups	68.384	260	.427		
Total	84.331	265			

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 2: Results from testing hypothesis using One- Way ANOVA

From the above table it is understood that the analysis is significant (P- value = .000 > 0.05) therefore the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The F value for the analysis is 7.462 which showed a low influence of the animated advertisements factors on consumer purchase decisions. The factors chosen for the survey include characters, music, product, illustrations, all and none one of them- for the test carried out for the first hypothesis and the results that the 'Characters' used in the advertisements have a higher impact than the others, in influencing the consumers purchase decision. Therefore from the analysis it can be concluded that features of animated commercials are attractive to consumers and influence their purchase decision. Animated commercials are effective in delivering the intended message to consumers is the second considered hypothesis. The below analysis showed that the variables have a low positive correlation (0.167 < 1) between the dependent variable (Information from advertisements) and the independent variable (Consumer purchase decision). This showed that consumers have slight contentment with the information they obtain from advertisements, and this has an impact on their intent to purchase the product being advertised. The analysis showed that the variables have a low positive correlation (0.167 < 1) between the dependent variable (Information from advertisements) and the independent variable (Consumer purchase decision). This reflected that consumers have slight contentment with the information they obtain from advertisements, and this has an impact on their intent to purchase the product being advertised.

		NINFO	PIN
Spearman's rho	NINFO	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.167
		N	266
PIN		Correlation Coefficient	.167
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.032
		N	266

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 3: Results from testing hypothesis using Correlation

		NINFO	NCPD
Spearman's rho	NINFO	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.359
		N	266

NCPD	Correlation Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.359	1.000
	N	.000	
		266	266

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 4: Results from testing hypothesis using Correlation

The above analysis showed that the variables have a low positive correlation ($0.359 < 1$) between the dependent variable (Information from advertisements) and the independent variable (Consumer purchase decision). This iterated that consumers are relatively satisfied with the information they receive from advertisements and have a significant impact on their purchase decision. Animated commercials are persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers was the third hypothesis.

		NINFO	NPREF
Spearman's rho	NINFO	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.337
		N	.000
NPREF	NPREF	Correlation Coefficient	.337
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	266

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 5: Results from testing hypothesis using Correlation

This test identified that consumers have a preference towards animated ads because of which they are more likely to purchase the product. The variables have a low positive correlation ($0.33 < 1$) between the dependent variable (Preference) and the independent variable (Consumer purchase decision).

		PIN	NPREF
Spearman's rho	PIN	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.187
		N	.016
NPREF	NPREF	Correlation Coefficient	.187
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.016
		N	266

Source: Results derived from SPSS

Table 6: Results from testing hypothesis using Correlation

The variables have a low positive correlation ($0.35 < 1$) between the dependent variable (Consumer purchase decision) and the independent variable (Information from animated advertisements). This means that they are satisfied with the information they get from animated advertisements and can have an effect on their purchase decision for the product. Analysis of the above data shows that animated commercials are persuasive in affecting the purchase decision of consumers. The other interpretations of the survey include that 54.2% Consumers claimed that animated advertisements gain more attention than any other format which was followed by live action ads, print ads etc. It is also inferred that animated ads attract the most attention from consumers as compared to alternative advertising methods 42.2% participants found animated advertisements to be entertaining. The results showed that more than half of the respondents (61.4%) were likely to skip a live video advertisement, over an animated advertisement. 77.2% felt that it was creative and fun way of promoting the products or services. 44% of respondents claimed advertisements are effective way to communicate about the product or service. 52.4% consumers felt that animated messages are more understandable. 30.7% respondents would consider the animated ads for purchasing the product or service. 33% consumers explained that ad appeals much better if telecasted in animation format. 41% consumers claimed that they remember animated ads more than any other format of advertisements. 63.6% - expressed moderate intention before they watched the ad. Animated advertisements are more likely to catch the viewer's eye and keep their attention, which can increase the likelihood that the viewer will remember the brand and the product being advertised. Animated ads have the ability to elicit positive emotions, such as happiness and amusement. This emotional response creates a favorable impression of the brand and the product being advertised, making it more likely that the viewer will consider purchasing it. Animated ads also improve a brand's image by creating a perception of modernity, creativity, and excitement. This helps to attract new

customers and retain existing ones. Animated advertisements are able to also enhance brand recall. The use of visual and auditory elements in animated ads helps to reinforce the brand and product in the viewer's memory, making it easier to remember the product when they are making purchasing decisions. Animated ads are able to positively influence purchase intent, meaning that they can make viewers more likely to consider purchasing the advertised product. This effect is particularly strong when the animation is directly related to the product being advertised. Overall, animated commercials have a positive impact on consumer buying behavior, by increasing attention, eliciting positive emotions, enhancing brand recall and value. However, it is important for marketers to consider the target audience and the appropriateness of animated ads for their brands and products.

Conclusion

To ensure that the animation is effective in influencing consumer behavior, it is important to keep the animation relevant to the product being advertised. Avoid using animation simply for the sake of entertainment, and instead, use it to enhance the message and benefits of the product. Animated ads are particularly effective in eliciting positive emotions such as happiness, amusement, and excitement. Incorporating these emotions into ads creates a favorable impression of the brand and the product being advertised. Animated ads should be consistent with the brand image and values. This consistency can improve brand recall and reinforce the brand's image in the minds of consumers. Animated ads offer a unique opportunity for creativity and innovation. Advertisers should take advantage of this by using high-quality animation, creative storytelling, and unique characters to make the ad stand out. The effects of animated advertisements on consumer buying behavior are substantial, and research has shown that they can be a highly effective means of reaching and influencing consumers. The key findings of this research suggest that animated ads can increase attention, elicit positive emotions, enhance brand recall, increase perceived product value and influence purchase intent. Additionally, some consumers may prefer animated ads over other types of ads, making them an ideal means of communicating brand messages and promoting products. One of the most significant advantages of animated ads is their ability to capture and hold the viewer's attention. Research has shown that animated ads are more likely to be watched in their entirety than other types of ads, and that they can effectively communicate complex or abstract concepts. By leveraging the power of animation to create compelling visuals and engaging storytelling, marketers can ensure that their brand messages are received and remembered.

Furthermore, animated ads can elicit positive emotions in viewers, such as happiness, amusement, and excitement. These emotions can create a favorable impression of the brand and the product being advertised, and can help to establish a connection between the consumer and the brand. Effective utilization of this emotional connection can influence consumer behaviour in strong ways, increasing brand loyalty and repeat business. Animated ads are also highly effective at enhancing brand recall and improving brand image. The use of unique characters and high-quality animation can create a strong association between the brand and the product, making the brand more memorable and recognizable. Additionally, animated ads can create a perception of modernity, creativity, and excitement, which can improve the brand's image and attract new customers. The research also suggests that animated ads can positively influence purchase intent. This means that viewers of animated ads are more likely to consider purchasing the advertised product. However, it is important to note that the effectiveness of animated ads depends on the appropriateness of the animation for the brand and product being advertised. It is essential to keep the animation relevant to the product, as using animation simply for entertainment value may not result in increased purchase intent.

Managerial Implications:

In order to understand how animated advertising affect customer purchasing behaviour, the study combines self-reported survey data with behavioural data, such as purchase behaviour. Finding out how customer engagement affects animated advertisement performance is one of the main goals of this study. This study explores the extent to which consumer interaction with animated commercials influences how well they can affect consumer purchasing decisions. The findings of this study help marketers and advertisers create effective advertising campaigns and advance our knowledge of how animated adverts affect customer purchasing decisions. It's critical for marketers to comprehend their target market and their preferences in order to maximise the impact of animated advertisements. By being consistent, a brand may increase consumer memory and strengthen its reputation. According to studies on how animated adverts affect customer purchasing decisions, they can be a very powerful tool for promoting goods and raising brand recognition. Marketers may capture more attention, provoke favourable feelings, improve brand memory, enhance brand image, and affect buy intent by utilising the power of animation to generate stunning images and engaging storytelling. The target audience gets influenced if the animation is relevant for the brand and product, and the overall quality of the advertisement all affect how effective animation is conducted. Marketers may produce animated advertisements that are more likely to change customer behaviour, raise brand awareness and engagement, and ultimately boost sales by adhering to best practises and using creativity.

Limitations and Future Study

The study's sample size can be a drawback because the findings might not be generalizable to the complete population. The findings' generalizability might be constrained as a result. Other contextual elements, such as a person's financial condition or personal preferences, that can affect a consumer's purchasing behaviour may not have been taken into consideration in the study. The study might just provide a snapshot of consumer behaviour and not account for animated commercials' long-term consequences. Although studies have demonstrated that animation can be a useful tool for promoting goods and raising brand recognition, it is still unknown whether particular animation types or quality levels are more beneficial than others. Future research could examine how various animation philosophies and levels of excellence affect consumer behaviour and whether some philosophies or levels of excellence are more suitable for particular products or target markets. The majority of animated ad study has been on how they affect consumers' intent to buy. Future research might look at the effects of animated commercials on awareness, consideration, and post-purchase behaviour, among other stages of the consumer experience. Future research might examine how effective animated advertisements are on different media, including social media, mobile devices, and game consoles.

REFERENCES

- History of advertising 101: What you need to know - G2. (2022). from <https://www.g2.com/articles/history-of-advertising>
- Jain, R., Luck, E., Mathews, S., & Schuster, L. (2022). Creating persuasive environmental communicators: Spokes characters as endorsers in promoting sustainable behaviors., from <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/1/335>
- Lakshman K, N. Sulaiman. A study on Dynamics and challenges on Traditional Banking and E-Banking services among Senior citizen's at Bangalore City. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, 931- 935. 2019.
- Lakshman K, N. Sulaiman A Study on Growth of Digital Payment System among senior citizen's in Selected Areas of Rural Bangalore, *Studies in Indian Place Names*, Volume 40, Issue 68, Issue, 684-688, May 2022.
- Lakshman K & Likitha S Influence of E-Banking Services Utilization among Working Women in Bengaluru, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Technology*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10777638>
- Need assessment through animation in TV food advertisements: An ... (2021), from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352119427_Need_Assessment_through_Animation_in_TV_Food_Advertisements_An_Experimental_Study
- Somra, A. (2020). Assessing the effectiveness of animated T.V. advertising with special reference to Vodafone animated commercials. Retrieved February 24, 2023, from https://ejmcm.com/article_5020.html
- Kochhar, D. (2019). Influence of Animation in Indian Advertising Industry . *Lovely Professional Univeristy* .